

ROLE OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS IN TAKING OFF THE INDIAN ECONOMY TO THE DEVELOPED COUNTRY STATUS BY 2025

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ABSTRACT

In spite of substantial economic growth of nations, there still persist conflicting views among developed and developing countries for retaining a strong intellectual property regime in their municipal laws. For instance, the debate on competition laws and feasibility of having monopolistic tendencies as emphasized by the jurisprudence of IP laws still appears to haunt the think-tank of developing nations like India. The fact that developing countries vary widely in the quality and capacity of their scientific and technical infrastructures, poses a major hurdle to the extent of applicability of IP, particularly, patent laws. Having a uniform IP standard across the globe undoubtedly seems to be an idealistic situation, but the issue certainly involves numerous micro and macro considerations which needs to be considered.

The aim of the present paper is to analyze the impact of a strong IP regime on the economic development of a nation. As is well understood, IP protection is an important determinant of economic growth. It helps entrepreneurs to recover costs of their innovative expenses. Undoubtedly, IP systems must be developed so as to bring in socio-economic well-being of the people. However, the incentives for the same needs to be analyzed critically considering the conflicting views of various stakeholders at the WTO platform.

Having strong IPR actually provoke IPR infringements in many developing nations also seems to be a serious issue which needs to be considered while comprehending the need for the strong IPR regime. The trade -off between unfair competition laws and IP also assumes importance of high magnitude and hence needs to be debated.

Keywords: Intellectual property, traditional knowledge, geographical indications, economic growth, competition act

Introduction

Intellectual Property has assumed pivotal importance throughout the world in the recent past. The “Intellectual Property” which was mainly the domain of World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) has also become part of World Trade Organization (WTO) regime in 1995. The TRIPS (Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights) of the WTO Treaty has laid down minimum standards

for the protection of Intellectual Property for member states to incorporate in their municipal laws.

Intellectual Property is an outcome of a human intellect. The main motivation for its protection is to encourage the creative activities and inventions. The role of intellectual property is *sine qua non* in the economic and technological development of a nation. The prosperity achieved by the developed nations is mainly the result of exploitation of their intellectual property.

In the absence of a law to protect intellectual property, there will hardly be any creative activity or inventions and as a result, the economic and technological development of a nation would come to a standstill. It is, therefore, essential to protect and promote intellectual property.

There has been a lot of controversy on the role of intellectual property protection (IPP) regime especially the patent system in fostering innovation, technology and industrial development of a country. IPP is expected to encourage innovation by rewarding the inventor. Strong IPP regime may also inhibit diffusion of knowledge and even technology development in the countries that are technology followers.

Countries have fine-tuned their IPP regimes as per their developmental requirements. Against this backdrop, the on-going attempt to harmonize and strengthen the IPP regimes worldwide, as per the TRIPs Agreement, which is widely seen to be adversely affecting the technological activity in developing countries by choking the knowledge spillovers from the developed world, besides having implications for the access and affordability to lifesaving drugs by the poor.

Outline of the present IP System in India

Uruguay round of GATT negotiations paved the way for WTO. Therefore, India was put under the contractual obligation to amend its Patents Act in compliance with the provisions of TRIPS. Accordingly, the Government of India brought into force the Patents Rules, 1972. These Rules were amended and replaced by the Patents Rules 2003 and further amended by the Patents (Amendment) Rules 2005, which includes the provisions relating to time-lines with a view to introducing flexibility and reducing processing time gradually for the patent applications, and also simplifying and rationalizing procedure for grant of the patent.

There are four Schedules to the Patents (Amendment) Rules 2005; the First Schedule prescribes the fees to be paid; the Second Schedule specifies the list of forms and the texts of various forms required in connection with various activities under the Patents Act as set out in this schedule. These forms are to be used wherever required and if needed, they can be modified with the consent of the Controller of Patents. The Third Schedule prescribes form of Patent to be issued at

the time of Grant of the Patent. The Fourth Schedule prescribes costs to be awarded in various proceedings before the Controller under the Act.

Outline of the present Economic Situation in India

India has indeed gradually moved on to a higher GDP growth path – 7 percent-plus and this has been made possible by many factors. The main factors are as under:

First, the evolving consumerism in the country due to rising disposable incomes of the middle class population which is propelling the economy to grow robustly in spite of external uncertainties/ shocks, e.g. rising oil prices.

Secondly, the country has been able to improve its saving and investment ratios in previous years, and these have now gone up to nearly 30 per cent of GDP and are showing upward direction.

Both, the emerging consumerism and the continuation of the present boom in investment domain could help to sustain 8-9 percent growth in the near to medium term, which would eventually result in even better business opportunities for the future.

Literature Review:

There have been numerous studies and analysis conducted to establish the relationship of IP with economic growth. Notably, the first cross-country research was developed by Rapp and Rozek (1990). They consulted the legal texts of each country's patent laws and made a rough assessment of their conformity with the minimum standards proposed by the US Chamber of Commerce.

However, due to the fact that their approach (RR approach) considered only the presence or absence of particular and specific features of patent laws, such as, working requirements, compulsory licensing, product patents for pharmaceuticals but did not considered 'enforcement effort or effectiveness', the lacunas were more than apparent. The RR approach was utilized by Ginarte and Park (1997) who examined the patent laws vis-à-vis five components of laws, namely, duration of protection, extent of coverage, membership in international patent agreements, provisions for loss of protection and enforcement measures.

Maskus and Penubarti's efforts in proving the direct and proportional linkage between IPR and GNP of a nation, stands as the most outstanding effort and deserves special mention. Using the parameters of GDP per capita, primary exports as a percentage of total exports, infant mortality rate and secondary enrollment ratios for 1965, in tracing the relation between IP and economic growth of a nation, the study pursued the analysis emphatically. Indeed their research was so close to perfection that they even succeeded in deriving the following logarithmic equation:

$$\text{Patent} = -0.51 + 0.49 \log(\text{Income}) R^2$$

Identification of Reforms towards IP-based Economic Development

Patent Regime before TRIPS

The positive effect of patents was not observed on research and economic development activities. Though the companies like Ciba-Geigy (Novartis), Hoechst (Aventis) and Boots has set up facilities in India, the Indian Private pharmaceutical sector did not pursue new drug R & D. The major research on drug development was started by Central Drug Research Institute; a public sector organization by developing moderate infrastructure.

(i) The Government of India did not provide adequate incentives to Indian companies to undertake new drug R&D.

(ii) There was a shrinkage of market opportunities of the Indian companies because they were not able to produce the new drugs invented abroad and protected by patents

Patent Regime after TRIPS :

Abolition of Product Patent Protection in 1972 operated as a pull mechanism and provided the Indian companies the space of operations and the opportunity to develop and innovate. Indian private sector has started investing in R & D for new drugs

IP and Economic Development: Relationship and Indicators:

Economic growth has been one of the major reasons and causes for the phenomenal rise in the study and importance of IP over the years. Protection and enforcement of IPR are the major components of international economic trade and scientific cooperation.

However, it is difficult to directly explain the apparent vital linkage between IP and parameters like the national income, rise in living standards, etc., which are among the most significant indicators of the economic status of a Nation. This is perhaps due to the diverse factors, like the variance in the cultural and socio-economic backgrounds of the people of India. The role of foreign direct investment (FDI) in a country's economic development is well known. Therefore, most of the studies and researches establishing the link between IP and economic growth have focused on FDI as an important parameter.

The protection of IPR has emerged as one of the most important considerations of contemporary international economic diplomacy. Multinational companies and firms

are becoming increasingly dependent upon copyrights, trademarks and patents to protect control of their goods and services in the global markets.

The implications of the above initiatives hence became the fundamental concern of many countries, especially India, upon whom the pressures from peers and the WTO are increasing in enormous proportions. The western nations' determination for prudent protection to overseas investments of their transnational corporations, and initiatives sponsored by the OECD, Multilateral Investment Guarantee Agency, the WTO's General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS) and Agreement on Trade-Related Investment Measures (TRIMS) signify the role of foreign direct investment in the economic development of a country and the intimacy of IPR with the same.

India's approach towards the entire issue of IPR vis-à-vis foreign direct investment has, fortunately, been in conformity with the above general assumptions. Indeed, the bilateral trade agreements with the European Union allowing foreign direct investment is only one of the major indications, primarily shown by the fact that EU is currently India's largest trading and investment partner with nearly a quarter of India's trade and about a seventh of actual foreign direct investment inflows.

Deliberations on modifying the present IP laws in consonance with TRIPS is a serious attempt to enhance FDI in the country. The Government of India has initiated plans for better understanding of IPR, such as, setting up of internal IPR protection teams, examining the work that can be copyrighted or patented, curbing the availability of unauthorized software products, performing periodic IP audits, etc., thus signifying the latent agenda to promote foreign direct investments in the country.

Analysis of reforms that exerted influence on economic development

Impact of IP Creation:

The patent production function or the knowledge function, relates the number of patent applications filed by a firm in a given year to the investment in R&D as well as gross domestic product GDP and other firm characteristics. However, in a developing country like India, firms do not have a long history of R&D or patenting. The technological spillovers are included in the data as a determinant of patenting is that Indian R&D is mainly adaptive rather than innovative. Past innovations induce shifts in technological opportunities because new discoveries can lead to an exploration of new research areas and increase technological opportunity. Since the benefits of R&D are not entirely appropriable, R&D spillovers occur when the fruits of a firm's research activity benefit other firms in the industry. The number of patents applications would increase with the ability of firms to assimilate R&D spillovers.

The number of patents obtained and applied is positively related to gross domestic product. Higher the GDP results in higher number of patents obtained and applied. The results also show that there is a positive relationship between the patents and R& D expenditure and IP index. The increase in R& D expenditure will lead to increase in the patents obtained and Applied. The results may improve after the introduction new patent policy 2005 and can be improved by studying the longer time period.

Impact on Business Activities:

Since the liberalization process began in 1991, India's real GDP has grown at an average annual rate of approximately 6-7%. Growth has been led by services and manufacturing, the two largest sectors, with agriculture growing much more slowly. In the longer term, the Indian Government is aiming for growth of between 8% and 10% per annum. For any country, total factor productivity (TFP) reflects the efficiency with which factors of production are used, and is thus a key determinant of an economy's performance, especially its international competitiveness. TFP should be distinguished from labour productivity (that is, the amount of output per employee), which is reflected in wage rates and thus living standards. Among the main sources of improvement in labour productivity are growth in investment, which increases the amount of capital that employees have to work with, and growth in TFP.

In the absence of accompanying improvement in TFP, however, higher labour productivity can only be achieved at the expense of lower capital productivity. One of the most important sources of TFP growth in the long run is technological progress. Analysis of data shows that average annual output growth in India increased from 4.5% during the period preceding the reforms of 1991 to 6.5% during 1993-06. Of this 2 percentage point increase, 1.2 points were attributable to improved TFP, which more than doubled from an average annual of 1.1% during 1978-93 to 2.3% during the period 1993-06. The rest of the rise was largely due to increased investments. Improved TFP contributed to roughly half of the increase in labour productivity, which almost doubled between the two periods; the rest of the increase was due mainly to higher investment. Improved TFP was also largely responsible for the substantial increase in the rate of growth of capital productivity.

Growth in both output and TFP has been much faster in the services sector than in industry. By contrast, growth in output and TFP in agriculture has slowed. It follows that the shifting of resources, especially labour, from agriculture, where two thirds of the labour force is currently employed, to the more productive services and industry sectors would contribute to faster overall growth in output and TFP in the economy as a whole.

Conclusion

It is well established beyond doubt that the potential economic and social repercussions of IP policy making are tremendous, and the claims have never been

higher than they are today. Increasing number of nations have begun to recognize this. Consequently, despite its long history, public interest in IP worldwide has reached unprecedented levels. It is an undisputed fact that wealth creation is shifting from a resource to knowledge base.

The economy seems to be experiencing radical changes due to paradigm shift in the approaches of business, commercial values of business and diversification of business. Such a shift is due to changes taking place in the business models and legal environment. One needs to locate the status of IP laws and understand the gravity of the role played by the same.

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